

Structural and spectral studies of 4-methylbenzylammonium nitrate crystal

R. Aarthi, P. Umarani, C. Ramachandra Raja*

Government Arts College (Autonomous), Kumbakonam -612002, Tamilnadu, India.

E mail id: crreja@rediffmail.com

mobile number: 99766 96277

Abstract

An organo-inorganic hybrid crystal fabricated from 4-methylbenzylamine cations and NO₃ anions has been synthesized by slow evaporation solution growth method. The single crystal X-ray diffraction method was employed to determine the structural parameters. It is found that the crystal belongs to monoclinic crystal system with space group P2₁/c. The unit cell parameters were also determined. The UV-Vis-NIR spectrum established the optical transparency and the lower cut off wavelength is found to be 230 nm. The vibrational modes of various functional groups are found by FTIR spectrum. The molecular structure of the title compound was established by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy.